

1 **Acrosomal status and PARP-1 nuclear markers could improve discrimination**
2 **of potential fertility in good-quality boar semen doses**

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25 **ABSTRACT**

26 Reproductive efficiency partly depends on boar semen quality. However, it is
27 challenging to predict sperm fertility once acceptable quality endpoints have been
28 met. This study aims to establish a link between different semen quality parameters
29 and farm fertility outcomes in semen doses selected for commercial use. We
30 analysed 105 ejaculates from 15 adult Pietrain boars, extended into 45 mL artificial
31 insemination (AI) doses. A total of 605 sows were inseminated (40.1 ± 7.8 females/
32 boar), and fertility, farrowing rate, and prolificacy data were recorded. Sperm
33 evaluation included sperm plasma analysis, kinematics, morphology, viability,
34 acrosome integrity, apoptotic-like changes, mitochondrial activity, and DNA damage
35 (DNA fragmentation poly-ADP ribose polymerase 1, PARP1, together with its
36 product, PAR, and its cleaved form cPARP). The sperm membrane and acrosome
37 were evaluated using the short hypoosmotic swelling test (sHOST) and the osmotic
38 resistance test (ORT). Fertility and farrowing rates exceeded 94%, with an average of
39 20.18 ± 2.03 piglets born/litter (average alive born: $87.75 \pm 5.61\%$). Negative
40 correlations were found between damaged acrosomes and ultrasound fertility
41 ($\rho = -0.240$, $p = 0.021$), farrowing rate ($\rho = -0.244$; $p = 0.019$), and total born ($r = -0.304$;
42 $p = 0.003$). Average born alive was positively correlated with plasma seminal
43 concentrations of protein ($r = 0.273$; $p = 0.009$), fructose ($r = 0.243$; $p = 0.024$) and
44 cathepsin B ($\rho = 0.257$; $p = 0.029$), but negatively correlated with apoptosis and
45 DNA damage nuclear markers, cPARP ($r = -0.295$, $p = 0.005$) and PAR ($r = -0.209$,
46 $p = 0.049$). However, regression models only showed significant results for predicting
47 the total born from damaged acrosomes and the alive born from cPARP. Since
48 semen quality and fertility were good, most parameters did not affect fertility

49 outcomes. Acrosomal damage follows previous studies as a reliable predictor of
50 reproductive outcomes, whereas cPARP shows potential as a novel biomarker.

51 **1 | Introduction**

52 Conventional sperm quality assessment detects sub-fertile boars and ensures sperm
53 quality of semen doses (Ruiz-Sánchez et al., 2006). However, their predictive value
54 is limited, so other cell and molecular parameters have been tested using flow
55 cytometry (Boe-Hansen & Satake, 2019). Chromatin status has been a promising
56 topic for discriminating among boars and ejaculates (Ausejo et al., 2022; Mateo-
57 Otero et al., 2022) and novel parameters such as poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase 1
58 (PARP1) activity (poly (ADP-ribose), PAR, (presence) or its cleaved form (cPARP)
59 have been proposed for this purpose (Casao et al., 2015).

60 Additionally, seminal plasma (SP) influences sperm function and reproductive
61 success. It contains a complex mixture of proteins, antioxidants, hormones, and other
62 molecules that influence sperm function, survival, and fertilization (Dyck et al., 2011;
63 Rodriguez-Martinez et al., 2021), as well as modulate the female reproductive tract
64 (Parrilla et al., 2020). Thus, combining the analysis of sperm parameters and seminal
65 plasma could improve the predictive power of semen testing (Llavanera, 2024).

66 Using data from commercial farms, this study explores the relationship between
67 sperm variables and SP components with fertility and prolificacy.

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69 **2 | Material and methods**

70 This study followed ARRIVE guidelines (Kilkenny et al., 2010), Council Directive
71 2008/120/EC (minimum standards for the protection of pigs), and Directive

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72 2010/63/EU (protection of animals used for scientific purposes). The Ethics
73 Committee of the University of Zaragoza approved the study (PI36/24).

74 **2.1 | Animals**

75 Fifteen young healthy Pietrain boars aged 681.4 ± 67.52 days were included (genetic
76 lines Nucléus: 10, weekly sperm collection, January-March 2022; and Batallé, four-
77 day collection, March-April 2022). Boar crates were at least 6 m^2 with *ad libitum*
78 water. Animals were fed once a day (commercial diet), and lighting and temperature
79 were controlled (20-22 °C).

80 **2.2 | Semen collection and seminal doses**

81 The double-gloved-hand technique was used for semen collection, discarding pre-
82 sperm and gel fractions. Semen was tested by CASA (Computer-Assisted Sperm
83 Analysis) in the same center to exclude ejaculates with <70% total motility and >25%
84 abnormal morphology. Magapor SL established additional exclusion criteria as
85 described previously (Ausejo-Marcos et al., 2024). Therefore, 105 ejaculates were
86 accepted for seminal doses preparation (3-9 ejaculates/boar for Nucléus and 6
87 ejaculates/boar for Batallé genetic lines).

88 The ejaculates were diluted to 45-mL seminal doses with a high-performance
89 commercial extender (Duragen®; Magapor SL, Ejea de los Caballeros, Spain) at
90 2.9×10^7 cells/mL and kept at 15-17 °C. For evaluation of conservation, two doses
91 were kept in the AI stud for 5 days. Evaluations were performed in an external
92 laboratory (cienciaNova, Magapor AIE, Zaragoza, Spain), which received two other
93 doses and undiluted ejaculate for assessing sperm parameters and seminal plasma
94 isolation. The remaining doses were sent to the sow farms for inseminations.

95 **2.3 | Sperm plasma analyses**

96 Ejaculates were centrifuged (1500×g, 10 min) to obtain SP, which was aliquoted and
97 kept frozen (-80 °C) until analysis.

98 SP analyses were carried out using commercial kits according to the manufacturer's
99 instructions. Protein concentration was assessed with the Micro BCA Protein Assay
100 Kit (ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA), and fructose, zinc, and citrate concentrations by
101 D-Glucose/D-Fructose, BROMO-PAPS, and Citrate/Citric Acid kits with an A15
102 Access Analyzer (Biosystems, Barcelona, Spain). Enzymatic activities were
103 assessed colorimetrically: superoxide dismutase (SOD) colorimetric kit and
104 mammalian β -Galactosidase Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific); Pig Epididymal
105 secretory GPX ELISA Kit (MyBioSource Inc, San Diego, CA) for glutathione
106 peroxidase 5 (GPX5); Cathepsin B Activity Assay Kit for Cathepsin B and Alkaline
107 Phosphatase Assay Kit for alkaline phosphatase (ALP) (Abcam, Cambridge, UK).

108 **2.4 | Sperm assessment**

109 *Motility and concentration*

110 Motility analysis was performed with a commercial boar-specific CASA (Magavision
111 ELITE®, Magapor). Samples were pre-warmed (15 min, 37 °C) and 3.5 μ L were
112 placed in a 20- μ m chamber (Magapor SL), recording at least 500 cells (60 fps, 1 s) at
113 $\times 10$ pHN. The CASA provided total (TMot) and progressive motility (PMot), fast,
114 intermediate, slow, and static spermatozoa, curvilinear (VCL, μ m/s), straight line
115 (VSL, μ m/s) and average velocity path (VAP, μ m/s), linearity (LIN, VSL/VCL, %),
116 straightness (STR, VSL/VAP, %), wobble (WOB, VAP/VCL, %), amplitude of lateral
117 head displacement (ALH, μ m), and beat cross frequency (BCF, Hz).

118 *Sperm morphology and acrosome status*

119 Sperm cells were stained (1:1) with an eosin-nigrosine solution (Magapor SL) and
120 examined under a bright-field microscope at $\times 1000$ for sperm morphology. At least
121 200 spermatozoa were counted per slide and the percentage of sperm with intact
122 acrosomes and total abnormal forms (AF) were recorded. Spermatozoa were
123 considered abnormal when they had head, midpiece, or tail defects, or cytoplasmic
124 droplets.

125 *Short hypoosmotic swelling test and short osmotic resistance test*

126 Sperm membrane functionality and acrosomal resistance were assessed using the
127 short hypoosmotic swelling test (sHOST) and the short osmotic resistance test
128 (sORT) (Rota et al., 2000), as previously described (Pérez-Llano et al., 2001). At
129 least 200 spermatozoa were counted per slide. Sperm with curled tails after sHOST
130 and intact acrosomes (acro%) after sORT were expressed as proportions.

131 *Flow cytometry analysis*

132 The membrane and acrosomal integrity, apoptosis and mitochondrial activity were
133 assessed with a BD Accuri™ C6 flow cytometer with BD software (Becton Dickinson,
134 Madrid, Spain), equipped with 2 laser sources (blue, 488 nm and red, 640nm) and 4
135 fluorescence detectors (blue line: FL1 533/30, FL2 585/40; FL3 670LP; red line: FL4
136 675/25). At least 20,000 events were recorded. Debris was excluded based on
137 forward scatter (FS) and side scatter (SS) characteristics.

138 *Sperm membrane and acrosome integrity*

139 Samples (5×10^6 cells/mL) were incubated (15 min 37 °C in darkness) with 16 μ M
140 propidium iodide (PI) and 15 μ g/mL FITC-PNA (peanut agglutinin) (Merck,

141 Darmstadt, Germany) and analyzed by flow cytometry (FL1 PNA and FL2 PI),
142 recording the percentages of viable (PI-) and acrosome-damaged spermatozoa
143 (PNA+).

144 *Apoptosis and mitochondrial activity*

145 Samples (5×10^6 cells/mL) were incubated (15 min, 37 °C in darkness) with 40 nM
146 YO-PRO-1 and 125 nM MitoTracker deep red (ThermoFisher) and analyzed by flow
147 cytometry (FL1 YO-PRO-1 and FL4 MitoTracker), recording the percentages of early
148 apoptotic (YO-PRO-1+) and high-mitochondrial activity spermatozoa (MitoTracker+)
149 (Mendoza et al., 2013; Nerin et al., 2018).

150 *Sperm chromatin assessment*

151 The Sperm Chromatin Structure Assay (SCSA) was used to assess DNA
152 fragmentation (Evenson, 2022). Samples were diluted with TNE buffer (0.01 M Tris-
153 HCl, 0.15 M NaCl, Na₂EDTA 1 mM; pH 7.4) up to 2×10^7 mL⁻¹ and stored at -80 °C
154 until processing in the reference laboratory (INDEGSAL, León, Spain). After thawing,
155 100 µL were treated with 400 µL of acid-detergent solution (0.1% Triton X-100,
156 150 mM NaCl and 80 mM HCl; pH 1.2) for 30 s and then with 1.2 mL of staining
157 buffer (6 µg/mL acridine orange, 100 mM citric acid, 200 mM Na₂HPO₄, 1 mM
158 Na₂EDTA, 150 mM NaCl; pH 6.0). Samples were run through a FACScalibur flow
159 cytometer (Becton Dickinson) with CellQuest v5 software. The blue laser excited
160 acridine orange, collecting the fluorescence emission with filters 525/50 (green) and
161 665/730 (red). At least 2,000 spermatozoa were counted within 3 min. DNA
162 fragmentation (%DFI) was calculated as the proportion of spermatozoa with high DFI
163 (red/total fluorescence). Sperm nuclear compaction was estimated by high DNA

164 stainability (%HDS) as spermatozoa with green fluorescence above 650 on a 1024
165 scale.

166 PARP-1 and its derivatives, cPARP and PAR, were detected using immunostaining
167 with validated antibodies (Abcam) as described previously, assessing samples with a
168 Cytex® Aurora spectral cytometer (Cytex® Biosciences, Amsterdam, The
169 Netherlands) using the SpectroFlo® v.3.3.0 software. Samples (100 µL) were
170 washed (PBS, 1000×g 11 min, 4 °C) and fixed (4% formaldehyde, 20 min). Samples
171 were washed and incubated with 10 mM dithiothreitol (DTT) (15 min, 37 °C) to induce
172 nuclear decondensation. They were then washed and permeabilized with a 0.1%
173 Triton solution (0.1% sodium citrate, 30 min on ice) and blocked with 4% BSA in PBS
174 (1 h). Samples were washed and incubated overnight at 4 °C with the primary
175 antibodies anti-PARP1 (436400, ThermoFisher), anti-cPARP (44-698G,
176 ThermoFisher), and anti-PAR (ab14459, Abcam), 1/200 in PBS. Samples were
177 washed and labelled with fluorescent secondary antibodies conjugated with Alexa
178 Fluor®: 647 for PARP1 (ab150111, Abcam), 488 for cPARP (ab150081, Abcam), and
179 568 for PAR (A11041, Invitrogen). After washing, samples were counterstained with
180 2.7 µM Hoechst 33342 (H342) and assessed (at least 5,000 spermatozoa per
181 sample). Debris was gated out as H342- and mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) and
182 ratios cPARP/PARP1 and PAR/PARP1 were recorded using Weasel v.3.7 software
183 (Frank Battye, Melbourne, Australia).

184 **2. 4 | Farm trial: insemination and monitoring of inseminated sows**

185 Sperm doses were sent to two commercial sow farms (size 2500-2700 sows) in the
186 northeast of Spain and applied by post-cervical artificial insemination (PCAI,

187 Magapor SL). Heat detection was done using a teaser boar, and only sows in heat
188 were inseminated.

189 A total of 605 DanBred hyperprolific sows were inseminated weekly in batches of 40–
190 55 (40.1 ± 7.8 sows/boar). Each female received semen only from the same boar
191 throughout the oestrus. Fertility and prolificacy data (average ultrasound fertility (%),
192 AUF, farrowing rate (%), AFR, total born, ATB, and born alive (%), ABA) were
193 recorded for each ejaculate.

194 **2.5 | Statistical analysis**

195 Statistical analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics 26.0 software (IBM
196 Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Normal distribution was tested by Shapiro–Wilk. Non-
197 normally distributed variables were transformed (\log_{10} , square root, or arcsine).
198 Descriptive statistics use mean \pm SD (standard deviation). Pearson's (r) and
199 Spearman's (ρ ; non-normal variables) correlation coefficients were used to estimate
200 the association between reproductive success and sperm parameters. Multiple
201 regression models were adjusted for the prediction of reproduction success
202 (response variables: AUF, FR, ATB or ABA) from sperm parameters (explanatory
203 variables) with a forward procedure (p values for F test 0.05 for entering and 0.10 for
204 leaving the model). Only variables significantly correlated with the dependent
205 variables were initially considered in the initial models. To avoid multicollinearity,
206 explanatory variables with correlations greater than 0.7 were excluded. The
207 significance level in all cases was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

208 **3 | Results**

209 Table 1 shows the overall sperm characteristics. Data for β -galactosidase, GPX5,
 210 cathepsin B and ALP were only available from a small portion of the ejaculates.
 211 Several variables (15) were not normally distributed (Shapiro–Wilks test, $p < 0.05$).
 212 Therefore, a \log_{10} transformation was applied to fructose, SOD, β -galactosidase, and
 213 GPX5 concentrations, as well as damaged acrosomes (%), early apoptosis (%),
 214 %DFI (%), and %HDS (%), the square root to protein and citrate concentrations, and
 215 the arcsine function to Acro (%), sHOST (%), sORT (%), viability (%), and
 216 mitochondrial activity (%). Table 2 shows results on reproductive success after PCAI.
 217 The association between variables (Table 3) was assessed by Pearson correlation (r)
 218 or Spearman (ρ ; non-normally distributed variables: AUF, AFR, and cathepsin B).
 219 Only significant r or ρ values are shown in Table 3 ($p < 0.05$).

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221 **TABLE 1** | Characteristics of ejaculates. Values are mean \pm SD (standard deviation. n :
 222 sample size)

Variable	n	Mean \pm SD
Protein (mg/mL)	104	41.92 \pm 20.341
Citrate (mg/dL)	105	167.8 \pm 89.930
Fructose (mg/dL)	99	4.3 \pm 1.850
Zinc (μ g/dL)	102	4298.31 \pm 1575.856
SOD (U/mL)	98	1.93 \pm 2.925
Beta-Galactosidase (nmol/min/mg)	75	15.89 \pm 27.453
GPX5 (\log_{10} ng/mL)	50	166.06 \pm 88.768
Cathepsin B (RFU)	69	21244.0 \pm 3315.76
ALP(U/mL)	18	5.33 \pm 2.910
pH	94	7.43 \pm 0.082
AF	103	16.6 \pm 5.49
Acro (%)	104	91.2 \pm 8.88
TMot (%)	104	91.08 \pm 5.241
PMot (%)	104	64.41 \pm 8.592

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Fast spermatozoa (%)	104	65.20 ± 14.878
Intermediate spermatozoa (%)	104	22.12 ± 8.974
Slow spermatozoa (%)	104	3.77 ± 3.145
Static spermatozoa (%)	104	8.91 ± 5.241
VCL (µm/s)	104	68.25 ± 10.951
VSL (µm/s)	104	30.80 ± 5.274
VAP (µm/s)	104	47.89 ± 8.321
LIN (%)	104	45.47 ± 6.483
STR (%)	104	64.85 ± 8.198
WOB (%)	104	70.13 ± 4.209
ALH (µm)	104	2.50 ± 0.295
BCF (Hz)	103	6.58 ± 0.381
sHOST (%)	101	73.7 ± 6.27
sORT (%)	96	80.2 ± 7.61
Viability (%)	104	90.81 ± 6.167
Damaged acrosomes (%)	104	12.23 ± 7.739
Mitochondrial activity (%)	104	90.59 ± 4.693
Early apoptosis (%)	102	9.90 ± 4.443
cPARP_MFI	102	11.53 ± 0.330
PARP1_MFI	102	12.22 ± 0.338
PAR_MFI	102	12.65 ± 0.439
cPAR/PARP	102	0.94 ± 0.027
PAR/PARP1	102	1.04 ± 0.032
DFI (%)	102	4.54 ± 6.383
HDS(%)	102	7.65 ± 1.680

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225 **TABLE 2** | Reproduction success characteristics. Values are mean ± SD (standard
 226 deviation) AUF: average ultrasound fertility (%) ; AFR: average farrowing rate (%);
 227 ATB: average total born; ABA: average born alive (%); n: sample size.

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Variable	n	Mean ± [Q1, Q2]
(%)	92	100.00 [100.00,100.00]
	92	100.00 [89.17,100.00]
	92	20.18 ± 2.029
	92	87.75 ± 5.607

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Variable	n	Mean \pm SD
AUF (%)	92	95.4 \pm 10.31
AFR (%)	92	94.3 \pm 11.10
ATB	92	20.18 \pm 2.029
ABA (%)	92	87.75 \pm 5.607

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234 **TABLE 3** | Significant correlation coefficients for reproductive success characteristics
 235 ($p < 0.05$). AUF: average ultrasound fertility (%); AFR: average farrowing rate (%);
 236 ATB: average total born; ABA: average born alive (%); Spearman ρ was estimated
 237 for AUF, AFR, and cathepsin B; Pearson r was calculated in the rest of the cases. n:
 238 sample size.

Fertility outcomes	Semen variables; fertility outcomes	n	Pearson r ; Spearman ρ	p -value (bilateral)
AUF (%)	Damaged acrosomes (\log_{10} %)	92	-0.240	0.021
	Average farrowing rate (%)	92	0.855	<0.001
AFR (%)	Damaged acrosomes (\log_{10} %)	92	-0.244	0.019
	Average ultrasound fertility (%)	92	0.855	<0.001
ATB	Damaged acrosomes (\log_{10} %)	92	-0.304	0.003
ABA (%)	Protein (sqrt mg/mL)	91	0.273	0.009
	Fructose (\log_{10} mg/mL)	86	0.243	0.024
	Cathepsin B (RFU)	58	0.257	0.029
	cPARP (MFI)	89	-0.295	0.005
	PAR (MFI)	89	-0.209	0.049

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242 Table 4 presents the significant regression models obtained for predicting ATB and
243 ABA (%) from models that include several explanatory variables, which have
244 previously demonstrated a significant correlation with these reproductive success
245 variables and are not strongly correlated among themselves.

246 No significant model was found for AUF and AFR.

247 The model for ATB was significant ($F_{1,90}=9.191$; $p=0.003$) when damaged acrosomes
248 ($\log_{10} \%$) were included as the only explanatory variable. However, the coefficient of
249 determination was low ($R^2=0.093$); only 9.3 % of the variation in ATB was explained
250 by this model.

251 For the ABA, cathepsin B (69 observations) was not considered as independent
252 variable because only a small number of data are available. On the other hand,
253 highly r value was obtained for PAR and cPARP ($r=0.708$; $p<0.001$), therefore only
254 cPARP, with more intense correlation with average born alive , was considered as
255 independent variable in the initial model, , together with protein and fructose
256 concentration. cPARP was the only one included based on higher and most
257 significant r (Table 3). The model was significant ($F_{1,80}=7.830$; $p<0.001$), however,
258 with a low coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.089$); this model explained only 8.9% of
259 the variation in ABA.

260 In both models, the negative estimators B (-2.111 ± 0.696 and -4.894 ± 1.749 ,
261 respectively) indicated that an increase in acrosomal damage or cPARP was
262 associated with a decrease in litter size or ABA, respectively.

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264 **TABLE 4** | Significant regression models ($p < 0.05$). ATB: average total born; ABA: average born alive (%); n : sample size, B:
 265 estimate for the explanatory parameters; SE: standard error for the estimate; 95% CI for B: 95% confidence interval for the
 266 estimate; LL and UL: lower and upper limits for CI; R^2 : coefficient of determination; ΔR^2 : change in R^2 when the last explanatory
 267 variable was included in the model; ΔR^2 p-value: degree of significance of such change.

Response variable	n	Explanatory variables	B	SE	p-value	95% CI for B		Beta	R^2	ΔR^2	ΔR^2 p-value
						LL	UL				
ATB	92	Intercept	22.280	0.720	<0.001	20.849	23.712		0.093	0.093	0.003
		Damaged acrosomes (\log_{10} %)	-2.111	0.696	0.003	-3.495	-0.728	-0.304			
ABA (%)	82	Intercept	114.092	20.173	<0.001	74.552	122.618		0.089	0.089	0.006
		cPARP (MFI)	-4.894	1.749	0.006	-8.322	-1.466	-0.299			

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271 **4 | Discussion**

272 This study shows that the evaluation panel in stud centers could be expanded to
273 predict reproductive outcomes; however, given the current strict quality controls for
274 sperm quality, any increases are small. In our case, fertility parameters were like
275 those reported and considered satisfactory in modern sow farms (Freyer, 2018). It is
276 possible that the evaluated variables would have a higher predictive power in cases
277 of lower fertility (other sow lines or summer stress).

278 A relevant finding was the significant association of sperm acrosomal damage (a
279 "classic" parameter for sperm evaluation) with the fertility variables and the litter size.
280 Previous studies have linked the acrosomal reaction to fertility in different species
281 (Bernecic et al., 2021; Pampiglione et al., 1993); in pig, a weak negative association
282 has been found between acrosomal damage, assessed by microscopy, and the
283 farrowing rate (Gadea et al., 2004; Galli & Bosisio, 1988). It is not surprising that the
284 association found in our study was similarly weak, since only ejaculates with less
285 than 20% acrosomal damage were used as part of the selection criteria (Ausejo-
286 Marcos et al., 2024). It is possible that using flow cytometry, with higher precision
287 than typical evaluations by microscopy, enabled the disclosure of this relationship,
288 even with good-quality semen doses.

289 Another important finding was the association between SP parameters, including
290 protein, fructose, and cathepsin B levels, and the number of born-alive piglets.

291 Although only part of the samples could be assessed for SP, this finding is still
292 relevant. Seminal plasma components interact with spermatozoa during ejaculation,
293 influencing motility, capacitation, transport, survival, and longevity, as well as through

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294 modulation of the female genital tract (González-Cadavid et al., 2014; Mogielnicka-
295 Brzozowska & Kordan, 2011; van den Berg et al., 2024). Considering SP proteins, a
296 more detailed analysis could help refine this relationship, given their diverse roles.
297 Indeed, no significant correlation was found between the enzymes SOD, β -
298 galactosidase and GPX5 and reproductive outcomes. The results for cathepsin B
299 deserve more attention, since higher levels have been previously associated with
300 low-quality ejaculates (De Lazari et al., 2019); on the contrary, our results show a
301 positive association with born alive that could be related to the use of only good
302 quality ejaculates, not seeing the negative association . In the case of fructose, this
303 metabolite supports sperm motility and fertilization in boars (Jones & Connor, 2000;
304 Tsujii et al., 2006), and it could be a biomarker of the good performance of the male
305 reproductive tract (specifically, the seminal vesicles).

306 Whereas many studies have identified DNA fragmentation as a critical factor
307 decreasing reproductive success, from mouse (Fernández-Gonzalez et al., 2008) to
308 human (Schulte et al., 2010), and even in rainbow trout (Pérez-Cerezales et al.,
309 2010), our study did not find significant correlations for SCSA variables. Interestingly,
310 PAR and cPARP, parameters related to the activation of PARP-1 and to the
311 activation of apoptotic pathways (Pascal, 2018), respectively, were negatively
312 correlated with the number of piglets born alive. Sperm chromatin is a relevant factor
313 in sperm fertility and offspring viability, but its structure complicates its analysis in pig
314 (Gosálvez et al., 2011). Therefore, there is an interest in new biomarkers in this
315 species, and the PARP-1 system could be a promising one (Lacalle et al., 2024).
316 Following the correlation analysis, the multivariate analysis delivered only two
317 models, with limited predictive power. Fertilization is a complex process, and sperm
318 quality is just one of the many factors involved (Gadea, 2005). Indeed, identifying the

319 association and potential predictive value of new biomarkers was the primary
320 objective of this study. For instance, membrane biochemical activity, mitochondrial
321 membrane potential, osteopontin, and GPX5 (Michos et al., 2021), bacterial diversity
322 and profile (Zhang et al., 2020), and epigenetic modifications such as differentially
323 methylated regions (DMRs) have been proposed in this sense (Pértille et al., 2021).
324 Acrosomal damage evaluated by flow cytometry and cPARP levels could be added to
325 this growing list, and its relationship with fertility tested in a fully controlled
326 experiment. Indeed, fertility and prolificacy are strongly influenced by sow-related
327 factors: housing (Verdon et al., 2015), weaning-to-estrus interval (Bortolozzo et al.,
328 2023), hormonal activity (Geisert et al., 2020), and lifetime performance (Koketsu et
329 al., 2020).

330 In conclusion, fertility and prolificacy showed significant associations with several
331 boar sperm parameters, but the predictive value of these associations was low.
332 These results would be expected when minimum sperm quality standards are met.
333 Nevertheless, our study, starting from an ample set of variables, proposes potential
334 new biomarkers for discriminating among good-quality semen samples.

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